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Amino Acids from *Leucas lanata*

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THE genus *Leucas*¹ belonging to *Labiatae* family comprises 100 species found throughout the world. The species, *Leucas lanata* Benth.^{1,2} is found in Tripura along with *L. aspera* Spreng. It is a perennial herb with much branches from a stout rootstock having white flowers in axillary dense whorls, which have calyx straight mouths and setaceous bracts. Tender shoots are used as vegetables and leaves, and used medicinally¹. To find out the diet value of the plant with respect to amino acid content, we investigated chemically for the first time the aerial parts of the plant and isolated fourteen amino acids among which six are essential. In this communication, we report the isolation, characterisation and relative occurrence of these amino acids.

The aerial parts of the plant, *L. lanata* were collected from Khayerpur area of Agartala in September, 1985. The air-dried milled aerial parts (1 kg) were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and 90% ethanol successively in a Soxhlet for 48 h each. The alcoholic extract was concentrated and decolourised by refluxing with a little charcoal. The greenish filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to a gummy residue (30.2 g). A part of the residue (1.5 g) was chromatographed^{3,4} through Amberlite IR 120(H). Working up the column for neutral and basic amino acids as described⁵ led to the identification of lysine, threonine and histidine by co-pc with authentic samples.

Another portion of the crude residue (2.0 g) was chromatographed through Amberlite IRA 400(OH) and elution with 2 N acetic acid for basic and neutral amino acids led to the characterisation of glycine, serine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid,

hydroxy proline, proline, alanine, tyrosine, tryptophan, methionine and phenyl alanine by co-pc with authentic samples.

The relative occurrences of amino acids in μg per g of air-dried aerial parts isolated through their ninhydrin complexes and estimated colorimetrically⁶ were found to be histidine, 6.80; lysine, 4.80; threonine, 2.40; aspartic acid, 2.28; proline, 2.18; alanine, 2.01; phenylalanine, 1.98; glycine, 1.60; serine, 1.40; tyrosine, 1.05; glutamic acid, 1.01; hydroxyproline, 0.93; tryptophan, 0.75 and methionine, 0.30. The amounts of glycine and serine may be inaccurate as their bands were very close in preparative pc. Among these, histidine, lysine, threonine, phenyl alanine, tryptophan and methionine are essential amino acids for human system.

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Amino Acids from *Spilanthes paniculata*

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THE genus *Spilanthes*¹ belonging to *Compositae* family comprises 60 species found in tropical America and exotic in other countries. The species, *Spilanthes paniculata* Wall. ex DC.^{1,2} is found in the jhum land and waste places of Tripura. It is an annual herb of 2.5–5 cm long with many branches and yellow paleae embracing flowers. The juice of this plant is used by the tribesmen in the relief of gum pain. We investigated chemically for the first time the aerial parts of the plant and isolated twelve amino acids among which six are essen-